

SOCIAL COMMUNICATION STUDIES

IMPACT OF ONLINE SHOPPING WEBSITE DESIGN AND LAYOUT ON CONSUMER TRUST AND ONLINE SHOPPING EXPERIENCE: STUDY ON UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

In the modern world, with the development and progress of the world wide web and internet technology, people are now having more convenience in terms of shopping. Especially with the creation of online selling platforms (e-commerce) and shopping websites, consumers can purchase products and services without even moving out of their houses. Thereby, such growth of online shoppers affected the e-marketing as well as its strategies and tactics. As, online stores and e-commerce websites are now trying to reach their consumers through the most effective ways and approaches. However, since online shopping stores are only limited to their websites/apps, the aim of this study is to find out whether the design and layout of online shopping websites are essential in establishing consumer e-trust and shopping experience. The findings of this study suggest that the website design and layout of online shopping website indeed have an impact on consumer e-trust and online shopping experience.

Keywords: E-Commerce, E-Trust, E-Shopping, Online Shopping, Shopping Experience.

Introduction & Background. The benefit of online shopping websites was mostly seen during the COVID-19 pandemic. As, almost 26% of world population was shopping online just in 2020 [6]. Moreover, according to the study done in US, almost 18% of adult population is shopping online minimum four times a month [6]. One of the most interesting studies done by Nasdaq (National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations) indicates that by the year 2040, 95% of people's purchases in the world will be online, which once again specifies the global prevalence of online shopping among people. Consequently, almost 94% percent of internet users do shop online.

Objectives. Earlier on, in store shopping used to be the most preferred type of shopping by almost everyone. The reason behind this was the availability of staff members that would assist the consumer, give personalized recommendations or help when needed. Moreover, traditional shopping even let people test out or try on products and services. However, with unstoppable progress in technology, the era of online shopping is starting to rise. The underlying cause is the convenience of online shopping with its prices, variety of products, and time saving nature. In addition, with the launch of chatbots and consumer reviews people can easily get information about the products and ask any type of questions. Despite all that, majority of world population still avoids shopping online, the most well-known reasons for it are the payment security concerns

and e-trust in e-shops [1]. Another reason is the irritating and poor website structure which makes consumers leave the website and feel aversion towards the specific e-store [8]. On account of mentioned consumer obstacles in online shopping, the objectives and central point of the research are to:

1. Examine if the design and layout of online shopping websites have an impact on consumer e-trust.
2. Analyse if online shopping website design and layout affect consumers' shopping experience.
3. Find out the impact of online shopping website design and layout on consumer shopping experience and on consumer e-trust.

Research questions and hypotheses based on the research objectives are specified below, thus, this study has below mentioned hypotheses and research questions that will be examined.

Research Questions:

RQ1: Do the design and layout of online shopping websites have an influence on consumer e-trust?

RQ2: Do online shopping website design and layout influence consumers' shopping experience?

Hypotheses:

H1: Design/Layout of online shopping websites have an impact on consumer e-trust.

H2: Design/Layout of online shopping websites have an impact on consumers' shopping experience.

Independent Variable: Website Design/Layout

Dependent Variable: Consumer E-Trust & Online Shopping Experience

Figure. 1 Conceptual Model of Research

Impact of online shopping website design/layout on consumer e-trust. It has long been a subject of discussion whether design of shopping websites have an essential impact on consumers' e-trust in company or brand. Several studies were done on this case and found a link between web design and consumer trust. Consumer trust has also been an issue in the advancement of online shopping websites, for this reason, consumer trust in online shopping websites, is called "e-trust", as, it is associated with website layout, its parameters, as well as with the quality of distributed information [9].

One of the recent studies shows that the colour of online shopping websites is playing a crucial role in building consumer e-trust [2]. Various researches indicate that consumers usually doubt the reliability of the company if the design as well as the layout of website is not welcoming or straightforward. In addition, the first impression of users is very important, as, the maximum time for the website visitors to get impressed by the website is just between 3 to 6 seconds [11]. For these reasons, companies, especially e-commerce businesses, must work carefully while designing their websites. Interestingly, there are more than 26 million e-commerce and online shopping websites in the world, and each day a new one is being created. However, the failure rate of these businesses is between 80% to 90% [5] and most of them fail in the first 120 days [10] with the one of the major reasons being the design of their website due to which consumers avoid shopping with the specific company.

Furthermore, in accordance with many studies, most users state that poor website design and layout of online shopping websites makes them stay away immediately due to the uncertainty and doubt in the security and privacy of financial information at the same time personal data [7]. Some internet marketers state that what website design should own is the simplicity and professionalism. Moreover, as previously mentioned, colour is very essential; especially blue and red colours are proved to increase the conversion rate of online shopping websites. In addition, several studies concluded that consumers feel safe and trust the company when they see high quality pictures of what they are purchasing, for this reason, high quality graphics and photos are very crucial. Otherwise, consumers easily become tentative about the reliability of the website and behave with uncertainty.

Not just this, according to Annexcloud, "Enabling consumer reviews on online shopping website makes users have trust and even loyalty" as, users are prone to immediately leaving the website if it is dishonest by avoiding review section. Other very key parts of online shopping websites for creating consumer e-trust are responsiveness, easy checkout, smooth navigation, as well as strong branding, because these are the details that create the feeling of trust in consumers towards the company. Hence, from what is claimed by these studies, design of online shopping websites is a crucial key factor in building consumer e-trust, therefore this correlation is brought out and accentuated in this research.

Impact of online shopping website design/layout on consumers' shopping experience. The design and layout of any kind of website have always played a crucial role for visitors of those websites. One of the reasons for such affirmation is because web design always says a lot about the business, it is the face of the company which consumers see first. Moreover, because of technological advancement, almost every person visits the company web page before visiting the actual store or firm. According to a recent study, web design gives the company brand personality and first impression to website visitors [4]. Another study reveals that the convenience of website usage is directly linked with the consumer satisfaction and company success [8].

Several studies indicate that, consumers enjoy their shopping more when the layout and representation of the website is simple and easy to use. For example, almost 50% of online consumer say that website design is important for company's brand. Not just this, many other studies show that consumers want short, correct, and detailed information about the product or service they are purchasing, also, 42% of consumers stated that they would leave the website if the overall design and layout was poor [3].

In addition, one of the world-known marketers Neil Patel clearly stated how online shopping websites can positively affect consumers' shopping experience. Firstly, Patel asserted that consumers care about the overall website design, and they want to see professionalism, effort and brand image. Secondly, the speed plays a significant role as previously mentioned, as well as product selection. For example, consumers do not want to spend infinite amount of time on describing what they are looking for, for this reason, the product

selection part should be simple and clear. Besides, consumers expect to see product page for each specific product, intending to read reviews, ask questions about the product, read description and details, and get informed about the brand. Lastly, Patel mentioned the importance of accessible transaction and payment. In other words, consumers do not expect to have trouble with payment and are looking forward to being able to pay with any kind of modern methods, especially fast and securely.

Moreover, American entrepreneur Matthew Toren says that consumers love exceptions and opportunities such as personalized recommendations. Toren's study showed that consumers expect the online shopping companies to know what each consumer wants and design their account pages based on each one's needs and wants. As, these are some of the ways consumer shopping experience is linked with the website design according to some researchers and professionals. Therefore, this study examines the vitalness of online shopping web design on consumer shopping experience and the connection between.

Research Design, Target Population & Data Analysis. This study is a quantitative study with a descriptive research design. The questionnaire is administered via Google Forms, as it is more convenient in terms of preparing and distributing to respondents. The scales measuring Consumer E-Trust, Online Shopping Experience as well as Website Design/Layout Satisfaction are used in the survey. The respondents choose the mostly used online shopping website/platform first then proceed with answering the questions while bearing in mind their mostly used e-commerce website. The survey also includes several introductory and general questions as well as consumer demographics questions. Furthermore, all the scales have Likert Scale answer options and snowball sampling technique is utilized. In addition, all the scales used in this study were highly reliable and valid and were taken from previous studies. The estimated questionnaire length (time to finish the questionnaire) was calculated to be between 6 to 10 minutes. On the other hand, data was analysed on SPSS statistical package. The target population for this study were university students studying in Azerbaijan. As there are almost 30.000 students studying in Azerbaijan, the needed sample size for this research was 380 to have a confidence level of 95% and the margin of error of 5%. However, in order to have more generalizable results with more statistical power and mitigated effect of any potential errors, 410 surveys were administered to students, out of which 403 were valid for analysis.

Findings. The findings of this study suggest that the website design/layout of online shopping website indeed has an impact on consumer e-trust and online shopping experience. As, when measuring the impact of the independent variable of website design/layout on dependent variables of consumer e-trust and online

shopping experience, the impact was statistically significant for both dependent variables. Therefore, the findings of this study indicate the importance of website design/layout of online shopping websites when it is about creating pleasant online shopping experience and consumer trust. Thus, this study's findings demonstrate the crucial role of the website appearance and arrangement on consumers during the e-commerce shopping process. Hence, all the two hypotheses of this study were supported according to which the design/layout of online shopping websites have an impact on consumer e-trust and that the design/layout of online shopping websites have an impact on consumers' shopping experience.

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